

December 13th: Cold-Stunning Predictive Panel

Click on images below to enlarge

Reminder of things to think aloud about when reviewing slides

Checklist:

- Review images and think aloud
 - Share interpretation
 - Review next slide
- Next Slide:
[December 13th Air Temperature Prediction](#)

Click on this link to go to next slide with December 13th air temperature content

Reminder of things to think aloud about when reviewing slides

Checklist:

- Review image and think aloud
- Share interpretation
- Go back to Predictive Panel [December 13th: Predictive Panel](#)

Click on this link to go to back to the December 13th Predictive Panel

Checklist:

Review Images:

- Cold-Stunning Model
- TWC Air Temp. Model

Answer Questions:

- What is your **interpretation** of the **model outputs**?
- What do you think is the **likelihood** of the cold-stunning threshold being crossed?

On a scale from 0 – 10

PAUSE

Please use this checklist when thinking aloud and answering these questions

[Click Here To Main Task →](#)

Click on this link to move to next forecast

[December 13th:
Predictive Panel](#)

December 13th: Cold-Stunning Model

Reminder of things to think aloud about when reviewing slides

Checklist:

- Review images and think aloud
- Share interpretation
- Review next slide

[Next Slide:
December 13th
Air Temperature
Prediction](#)

Click on this link to go to next slide with December 13th air temperature content

Upper Laguna Madre Temperatures

When predictions start

Temperature Legend

Predicted Water	Predicted Air (NWS Forecast - NDFD)
Observed Water	Observed Air
	Interpolated Air

Cold-Stunning Model Legend

[Previous Slide: December 13th Cold-Stunning Model](#)

December 13th: TWC's Air Temp. Model

Click on this link to go back to previous slide with December 13th Cold-Stunning Model

Reminder of things to think aloud about when reviewing slides

The Weather Company's (TWC's) Air Temperature Model Legend

Checklist:

- Review image and think aloud
- Share interpretation
- Go back to Predictive Panel [December 13th: Predictive Panel](#)

Click on this link to go back to the December 13th Predictive Panel

December 16th: Cold-Stunning Predictive Panel

Checklist:

Review Images:

- Cold-Stunning Model
- TWC Air Temp. Model

Answer Questions:

- What is your **interpretation** of the **model outputs**?
- What do you think is the **likelihood** of the cold-stunning threshold being crossed?

On a scale from 0 – 10

PAUSE

[Click Here To See Next Forecast →](#)

[HELP Button: Previous Predictive Panel ←](#)

← [Click here if you went too far ahead and need to go back to the previous Predictive Panel](#)

December 16th: Cold-Stunning Model

Upper Laguna Madre Temperatures

Checklist:

- Review images and think aloud
- Share interpretation
- Review next slide

Next Slide:
December 16th
Air Temperature
Prediction

Temperature Legend

- Predicted Water
- Observed Water
- Predicted Air (NWS Forecast – NDFD)
- Observed Air
- Interpolated Air

Previous Slide: December 16th
Cold-Stunning Model

December 16th: TWC's Air Temp. Model

Checklist:

- Review image and think aloud
- Share interpretation
- Go back to Predictive Panel [December 16th: Predictive Panel](#)

Temperature Legend

December 19th: Cold-Stunning Predictive Panel

Checklist:

Review Images:

- Cold-Stunning Model
- TWC Air Temp. Model

Answer Questions:

- What is your **interpretation** of the **model outputs**?
- What do you think is the **likelihood** of the cold-stunning threshold being crossed?
On a scale from 0 – 10

PAUSE

[Click Here To See Next Forecast →](#)

HELP Button: [Previous Predictive Panel](#) ←

December 19th: Cold-Stunning Model

Upper Laguna Madre Temperatures

Temperature Legend

Checklist:

- Review images and think aloud
- Share interpretation
- Review next slide

Next Slide:
[December 19th
Air Temperature
Prediction](#)

Previous Slide: December 19th
Cold-Stunning Model

December 19th: TWC's Air Temp. Model

Temperature Legend

Checklist:

- Review image and think aloud
- Share interpretation
- Go back to Predictive Panel [December 19th: Predictive Panel](#)

December 21st: Cold-Stunning Predictive Panel

Checklist:

Review Images:

- Cold-Stunning Model
- TWC Air Temp. Model

Answer Questions:

- What is your **interpretation** of the **model outputs**?
- What do you think is the **likelihood** of the cold-stunning threshold being crossed?
On a scale from 0 – 10

PAUSE

[Move on to Additional Water Temperature Information →](#)

HELP Button: [Previous Predictive Panel](#) ←

December 21st: Cold-Stunning Model

Upper Laguna Madre Temperatures

Temperature Legend

Checklist:

- Review images and think aloud
- Share interpretation
- Review next slide

Next Slide:
[December 21st
Air Temperature
Prediction](#)

December 21st: TWC's Air Temp. Model

Temperature Legend

Checklist:

- Review image and think aloud
- Share interpretation
- Go back to Predictive Panel [December 21st: Predictive Panel](#)

Additional Water Temperature Prediction Information

(Please click on images or the green links below to enlarge each)

[Water Temperature Predictions with Percent Chance of Threshold Crossing](#)

[Percent Chance of Threshold Crossing Table](#)

Chance Water Temperatures Below Sea Turtle Threshold
Valid 2/2 through 2/8

Thursday Feb. 2nd								Friday Feb. 3rd							
12AM	3AM	6AM	9AM	12PM	3PM	6PM	9PM	12AM	3AM	6AM	9AM	12PM	3PM	6PM	9PM
0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	6%	29%	60%	70%	71%
Saturday Feb. 4th								Sunday Feb. 5th							
12AM	3AM	6AM	9AM	12PM	3PM	6PM	9PM	12AM	3AM	6AM	9AM	12PM	3PM	6PM	9PM
63%	87%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	99%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%
Monday Feb. 6th								Tuesday Feb. 7th							
12AM	3AM	6AM	9AM	12PM	3PM	6PM	9PM	12AM	3AM	6AM	9AM	12PM	3PM	6PM	9PM
100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	81%	52%	60%	88%	98%	98%	98%	76%	26%
Wednesday Feb. 8th															
12AM	3AM	6AM	9AM	12PM	3PM	6PM	9PM								
6%	8%	10%	4%	1%	0%	0%	0%								

Click here to see [Additional Water Temperature Prediction Information slide](#)

[Water Temperature Predictions & Estimates of Cold-Stunning Timing](#)

Start of Cold-Stunning Event
(based on Sea Turtle (46°F) Threshold)

Earliest Threshold Crossing (5th Percentile)
3/3/26 0600 UTC

Most Likely Threshold Crossing (50th Percentile)
3/3/26 1300 UTC

Latest Threshold Crossing (95th Percentile)
3/3/26 0500 UTC

End of Cold-Stunning Event
(based on Sea Turtle (46°F) Threshold)

Earliest Threshold Crossing (5th Percentile)
3/6/26 2100 UTC

Most Likely Threshold Crossing (50th Percentile)
3/7/26 2000 UTC

Latest Threshold Crossing (95th Percentile)
3/8/26 0800 UTC

Water Temperature Predictions

Valid 2/2 through 2/8

WATER TEMPERATURE PREDICTION LEGEND

- 50th Percentile (Median) Prediction
- 5th – 95th Percentile Prediction Range
- 25th – 75th Percentile Prediction Range

Percent Chance Below Sea Turtle Threshold (46°F)

2026

Click here to see

[Additional Water Temperature Prediction Information slide](#)

Chance Water Temperatures Below Sea Turtle Threshold

Valid 2/2 through 2/8

Thursday Feb. 2nd								Friday Feb. 3rd							
12AM	3AM	6AM	9AM	12PM	3PM	6PM	9PM	12AM	3AM	6AM	9AM	12PM	3PM	6PM	9PM
0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	6%	29%	60%	70%	71%
Saturday Feb. 4th								Sunday Feb. 5th							
12AM	3AM	6AM	9AM	12PM	3PM	6PM	9PM	12AM	3AM	6AM	9AM	12PM	3PM	6PM	9PM
63%	87%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	99%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%
Monday Feb. 6th								Tuesday Feb. 7th							
12AM	3AM	6AM	9AM	12PM	3PM	6PM	9PM	12AM	3AM	6AM	9AM	12PM	3PM	6PM	9PM
100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	81%	52%	60%	88%	98%	98%	98%	76%	26%
Wednesday Feb. 8th															
12AM	3AM	6AM	9AM	12PM	3PM	6PM	9PM								
6%	8%	10%	4%	1%	0%	0%	0%								

Click here to see
[Additional Water Temperature Prediction Information slide](#)

Water Temperature (°F)

Start of Cold-Stunning Event
(based on Sea Turtle (46.5°F) Threshold)

Earliest Threshold Crossing (5th Percentile)
 2/3/26 0600 UTC

Most Likely Threshold Crossing (50th Percentile)
 2/3/26 1300 UTC

Latest Threshold Crossing (95th Percentile)
 2/4/26 0300 UTC

End of Cold-Stunning Event
(based on Sea Turtle (46.5°F) Threshold)

Earliest Threshold Crossing (5th Percentile)
 2/6/26 2100 UTC

Most Likely Threshold Crossing (50th Percentile)
 2/7/26 2000 UTC

Latest Threshold Crossing (95th Percentile)
 2/8/26 0900 UTC

Thurs 2/2 Fri 2/3 Sat 2/4 Sun 2/5 Mon 2/6 Tues 2/7 Wed 2/8 Thurs 2/9
2026

WATER TEMPERATURE PREDICTION LEGEND

	50 th Percentile (Median) Prediction		Critical Cold Water Period		Start of Cold-Stunning Event Prediction Range
	5 th – 95 th Percentile Prediction Range		25 th – 75 th Percentile Prediction Range		End of Cold-Stunning Event Prediction Range

Click here to see [Additional Water Temperature Prediction Information slide](#)